

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SYSTEMS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INTELLIGENT TRANSPORT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Purpose – This article presents the applications of Artificial Intelligence in the development of Intelligent Transport Systems.

Methodology / approach – The methodology proposed in this article is based on the analysis of Artificial Intelligence algorithms for road traffic control and prediction. Image processing methods and polynomial prediction analyzes are applied, and their results contribute to the measurement of performance in road traffic prediction.

Findings – Based on the measurements of the processes undertaken by the authors, a methodology - was applied within the Traffic Management Center in Bucharest, to increase traffic management.

Research limitations / implications – The paper offers some concrete solutions obtained at a department level. These solutions based on a new approach to performance measures are developed in accordance with ITS requirements.

Practical implications – The practical aspects approached by the authors are related to the identification of the most problematic obstacles encountered in the implementation of performance management in ITS using a new methodology based on Artificial Intelligence.

Originality / value – The methodology based on the AI-oriented approach to classification and prediction can be implemented for measuring, evaluating and improving traffic using ITS strategies.

Key words: artificial intelligence system, expert system, intelligent management model.

Introduction

We live in such a complex world, in which human reason can hardly respond to the challenges posed by the rapid and permanent changes that are taking place in the economy. In the context of the knowledge-based economy, the use of information systems determines not only the development of companies, but also, in many cases, their survival, which depends on making the right decisions at the right time. For these reasons, artificial intelligence is increasingly present in economic activity and for Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS).

Conceptual approaches to artificial intelligence

The term "artificial intelligence" was introduced by John McCarthy in 1956, being defined as "the science and engineering of producing intelligent machines." Artificial Intelligence is a vast field that deals with the use of computers to solve problems / tasks that require human intelligence. It is known that there are many problems that require intelligence, but that can be solved very easily with the help of a computer, for example complex arithmetic. On the other hand, there are a few problems that people can easily solve without much thought, such as facial recognition, but which are extremely difficult to automate. Artificial intelligence deals with solving such difficult tasks, which require a complex and

sophisticated reasoning process. People may be interested in automating human intelligence for several reasons. One reason would be a better understanding of human intelligence. In this context, theories of human intelligence can be tested and developed by creating programs (software) that simulate aspects of human behavior. Another reason would be to have computers and smart programs. Even if it were making such computers, we cannot be sure that these programs accurately simulate human reasoning, but by studying human reasoning can be developed useful techniques for solving difficult problems specific to people. All this contributes in different ways to our understanding of how we can act and communicate intelligently and effectively. Understanding these areas helps us use computers to perform tasks and solve tasks issues that require intelligence. According to Ioniță Silviu (2015), it can be said that the year 1981 is the beginning of a promising stage for the evolution of artificial intelligence.

The development of artificial intelligence is reflected in complex and multidisciplinary practical algorithms: knowledge-based systems, cognitive systems, intelligent machines, intelligent agents. According to Raymond Kurzweil (2013), the concept of artificial intelligence refers to "the art of creating machines that perform functions that would require intelligence if they were performed by humans." Horia Pop (2018) reveals that artificial intelligence is a field of research whose purpose is to study and model intelligence, by creating systems capable of performing intelligent activities. Currently, Artificial Intelligence System (AIS) systems are widely used to automate decision-making in various economic fields.

Figure 1. Artificial Intelligence System (AIS) architecture.

AIS methodological basis

The activity of economic entities requires a very large number of decisions in the process of attracting and using the factors of production. The formalization of the decision-making process is possible due to the principles of recognition of the situation or objects of activity (Thorisson K, 2007). Each situation can be characterized by the description presented by a certain set of values of the indicators or properties regarding the introduction of AIS, as well as by a complete description of the subsequent actions at the exit (Fig.1). Thus, the AIS provides for the recognition of the situation and the decision on other actions, the implementation of the functions of the expert system (OECD, 2019).

Artificial intelligence systems can be entrusted with such tasks: choosing the investment project, investor, carrier, supplier, choosing product distribution options, evaluating product quality, forming transport tariffs according to product characteristics, etc. AIS can be used both in tactical operational activity and in strategic planning activities for optimal decision making.

The task of recognizing objects, such as identifying the economic situation at the macroeconomic level or the loading time of means of transport at the microeconomic level, requires a gradual solution of many theoretical tasks. In the first stage it is taken into account that each object is defined by the values of many properties, or signs, that form the indicative space. Thus, it is impossible to determine an a priori information content of the individual characters, from the point of view of the separability of the object classes, as well as the necessary number of the most informative features.

The *first phase* of AIS construction for each set of object classes is required to solve the problem of choosing the working characteristics of the system, which describe the recognition of the most informative object. In economic activity, the task of choosing the working characteristics of the system can also be focused on selecting the indicators of superior quality performance in the economic system, or the so-called KPI indicators.

Solving the task of choosing operating systems includes the following steps:

1. *Determining an a priori vocabulary of indicators*, i.e. choosing the range of indicators that characterize the recognition of objects, to classify them. Usually, an a priori dictionary includes all the significant features available for quantification.
2. *Choosing the way of coding the meaning of the indicators* and the way of describing the object in the form of a code - the indicative word, convenient for the computer system. Thus, it is necessary to take into account the fact that some indicators are quantitatively characterized by numbers, and some indicators may be of a qualitative or structural nature.
3. *Determining the values of the intervals of the range of changes of each indicator* in order to codify it according to the principle of adaptive quantification. This involves setting thresholds for these meanings of the indicators, above and below which the corresponding object recognition classes differ.
4. *The comparative evaluation of the informativeness* of the a priori vocabulary indicators in relation to the recognition target, taking into account the selected coding method and the established intervals. Zero informativeness means the total absence of the contribution of this indicator to the recognition of the object, and the singular informational content corresponds to the case when according to the values of an indicator a complete classification (recognition) of the objects can be achieved.
5. *Selection of the working system* of the necessary and sufficient indicators for the full recognition of all objects. This step is accomplished by sequential addition to the most informative indicators, which provide the broadest (informational) pairs of properties. Then the index that forms the most informative triplet, etc. is selected, until the combination of indices that provide a unique information content is identified, namely: those that ensure full recognition of the object. The selection of the working system of the indexes minimizes the length of the indicative words, the introduction of the object recognition algorithm.

During the *second phase* of construction of the AIS it is necessary to form an object recognition algorithm, obtained in the first phase of the indicative space. During AIS work, objects or work situations appear at the entrance, the description of which is different from those of the initial stage. This determines the need to develop procedures for studying the recognition algorithm.

The recognition subsystem can use the learning algorithm, built on the theory of image recognition and using the adaptive weighting coefficients, established according to the category of the indicative word formed in the first stage.

The recognition process consists in calculating the values of the decisive function of the classified object according to all possible membership categories. The decision is made in favor of the class, for which the value of the decisive function is maximum. In case of recognition error, the learning process takes place; thus, the weighting coefficients are adjusted.

As a model of intelligent strategic management can be proposed a model with adaptive structure, which takes into account the factors of the external environment and the internal strategic tasks chosen on the basis of competition.

The intelligent control scheme includes the following units (Gallieres R, 1998):

1. *Preliminary assessment unit* (analysis of the political, technological, economic and social dimensions of the environment, PEST):
 - 1.1. Determining the objectives of the system.
 - 1.2. Choice of strategy.
 - 1.3. Determining internal opportunities and environmental threats.
 - 1.4. Identifying the advantages of the system (considering the size, distribution of resources, strengths and weaknesses of the company (SWOT)).

The results of the work of the preliminary assessment unit are coded according to the mechanism of formation of the indicative words for estimating the situation.

2. *Selection unit* (guaranteeing the choice of the optimal strategy):
 - 2.1. Examining alternatives.
 - 2.2. Choice of strategy.

The selection unit is implemented using a situation recognition algorithm, which extracts the necessary strategic decisions from the economic knowledge database.

3. *Implementation unit* (formation of the organizational structure, adequate strategy, allocation of human, material, financial and intellectual resources, in accordance with the requirements of the strategy):

- 3.1. Elaboration of the structure and climate of the organization.
- 3.2. Development of medium- and short-term policies, plans and programs.

The implementation unit is included in the information system and integrated with the knowledge base at the level of the expert operational management system.

4. *Evaluation unit* (ensuring the achievement of strategic goals):

- 4.1. Strategy evaluation.
- 4.2. Transition to unit 1 for changes in strategy and repetition of the management cycle.

This model requires a change in the internal structure of the information system, in line with current perspective and tasks. An indispensable condition for this is the existence of a strategic center, the formation of strategy in a continuous way.

AIS is integrated into the planned economic information system, based on the analytical information center (Liebowitz J, 1998) and can be used by participants in regional economic activities for their own purposes. At the level of individual organizations, the mechanism for classifying situations that require strategic decision making is their information base (Morabito J, 1999).

AI techniques in Intelligent Transportation System

Intelligent transport systems are applications of electronics, IT and communications in the field of transport whose major objectives are to reduce the negative effects of the transport activity (accidents, material losses, additional costs, pollution) and increase the efficiency of this activity. The term Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) originated in the United States and was originally used in road transportation to define traffic light and traffic management equipment and facilities. "Intelligence" at that time was given using electronics in the field of transport and was more a term imposed by marketing and not a term imposed by technology.

Figure 2. Chart of ITS services and AI systems.

Many ITS applications now use solutions based on artificial intelligence (AI - Artificial Intelligence), Data Mining, Big Data and so-called smart technologies. This means that the term Intelligent Transport Systems is defined by the technologies used and not by marketing tools. Figure 2 shows a Chart of ITS services and systems, as found in the studied works.

Research Methodology: Developing a traffic control application (the values generated by the Count Objects)

Semantic segmentation is the task of labeling images with semantic classes at the pixel level. It provides a high-level representation and can play an important role in the semantic perception and understanding of the environment. The main objective is to obtain a solution of high accuracy and precision at a low calculation cost, which would allow running in real time. This can be done using robust and time-efficient features and classification schemes. Cars, pedestrians and objects in traffic environments are limited by spatial and geometric constraints. We define such constraints and incorporate them into perception solutions in the form of additional context channels in addition to the filtered feature channels. In this way we can allow classifiers to learn the context for different types of objects or semantic classes. Context features can also speed up the prediction process. In the case of soft-cascade decision trees, the prediction is stopped if the intermediate prediction score falls below a certain threshold (L. Zhu, 2014). Context features can stop prediction at an early stage if the context is not appropriate for a semantic class. In our experiments for semantic segmentation we used the following contexts:

- 2D spatial: vertical and horizontal position in the image
- Spatial 3D: 3D position x, y, z, dense interpolated representation from stereo video cameras
- 3D size: the height and width in 3D of the groups of super-pixels

To generate semantic segmentation, we train an individual binary pixel classifier for each semantic class. We propose the use of multi-radius classification features, extracted from the feature channels. We classify individual pixels using the values of the surrounding pixels in the feature channels. The nearest points capture the local structure, while the distant ones capture the context. To capture the features at different radii, we extract them with a grid using different sampling rates. We use a 13 x 13 grid around the pixel of interest and apply sampling using a step rate of one, two, four and eight pixels, resulting in 676 points from each individual channel. Four grids with different sampling rates cover a region of 13 x 13, up to 104 x 104 pixels in the input image. To obtain powerful classifiers, train 2048 7-level decision trees for each semantic class. After training the classifiers we can generate semantic segmentations (GAs, Li et al. 2016). The results of the mathematical simulations are shown in Figures 3 (a) and (b). Figure 4 shows the results obtained for real-time video analysis for the counting object and traffic flow.

Figure 3. mathematical simulations. (a) The values generated by the “count objects” and (b) Fitting a 6-degree polynomial decomposition.

Figure 4. Count Object & Traffic Flow Detection from highway.

Conclusions

The sharp evolution of information technologies has led to the emergence of technical systems that tend to fundamentally change the way people live and even offer new models of economic activities. Intelligent systems can generate conclusions based on built-in or externally provided knowledge. The design and development of smart systems for optimal decision making are indispensable for the efficiency of economic activity. Artificial intelligence is no longer just a game of imagination or a simulated software paradigm, but an opposition to boosting economic efficiency. The clear trend of super-technology will lead human society to cooperate with increasingly intelligent systems, as intelligent as man, maybe even super-intelligent. In this article we have studied the applications of artificial intelligence with applicability in ITS management and we have proposed a solution for traffic prediction based on AI algorithms. Modern transport systems include a wide and constantly evolving suite of technologies and applications: from real-time traffic information, electronic tickets, to automatic passenger counting and traffic forecasts based on artificial intelligence. Transforming a city's transportation network into a smart system offers benefits on multiple levels: revenue growth, active contribution to raising the standard of living in the municipality and citizens' perception of the authority's concern for good governance, catalyst for a healthy economic life of the municipality, improving the efficiency and operational performance of the transmission network, in particular due to reduced costs, increasing passenger mobility and comfort, increasing the use of the transport system.

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